

Quantitative RT-PCR analysis and immunohistochemical localization of HSP70 in sea bass *Dicentrarchus labrax* exposed to transport stress

C. Poltronieri,¹ L. Maccatrozzo,¹ C. Simontacchi,¹ D. Bertotto,¹ B. Funkenstein,² M. Patruno,¹
G. Radaelli¹

¹ Department of Experimental Veterinary Sciences, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Padua, Italy;

² Department of Marine Biology and Biotechnology, Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research, National Institute of Oceanography, Haifa, Israel

Abstract

In aquaculture, fish are exposed to stressful conditions, which cause an increased synthesis of heat shock proteins (HSPs) at the cellular level. In this work we considered the expression of the constitutive and inducible forms of HSP70 as an indicator of stress caused by transport, during development of the sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), a teleost fish of high value for aquaculture. Qualitative RT-PCR analysis revealed expression of inducible HSP70 gene in larvae and fry (25, 40 and 80 days) as well as in adult tissues (liver, brain, muscle, gills, kidney, gonads, heart, spleen and skin) of both control and stressed animals. Expression of inducible HSP70 mRNA examined in different adult tissues by Real-Time PCR, was significantly higher in skin and skeletal muscle of stressed animals than in controls. Immunolocalization of inducible and constitutive forms of heat shock protein 70 (HSP70 and HSC70), reported here for the first time, demonstrated an ubiquitous distribution of HSC70 protein in several tissues of both stressed and control animals (at all stages), while inducible HSP70 protein was found only in skeletal muscle of stressed animals. In all stressed animals, regardless of their developmental stage, cortisol levels were higher than in control animals.